

Archiving, sharing and discussing research data on Eastern Europe, South Caucasus and Central Asia

Data Review

Data Citation

Anhelina Hrytsei (2025): The Aid Worker Security Database (published on Humanitarian Outcomes), v. 1.0, Discuss Data, <https://doi.org/10.48320/E7567B74-A162-47BC-9A41-3A87DAEF8FF3>

Abstract

The Aid Workers Security Database is a publicly available record of incidents involving violence against or the detention of aid workers in countries with a humanitarian presence. It covers the period from 1997 to 2025, and data collection remains ongoing. The database was created and is maintained by Humanitarian Outcomes, a UK-based research and policy consultancy for humanitarian organizations. As of November 2025, it includes 5,150 incidents coded across 44 variables.

Licensed as Attribution and Share Alike: Open Data Commons Open Database License (ODbL) ("share-alike")

Data Review:

Aid Worker Security Database

The Aid Workers Security Database is a publicly available record of incidents involving violence against or the detention of aid workers in countries with a humanitarian presence. It covers the period from 1997 to 2025, and data collection remains ongoing. The database was created and is maintained by Humanitarian Outcomes, a UK-based research and policy consultancy for humanitarian organizations. As of November 2025, it includes 5,150 incidents coded across 44 variables.

Methodological Foundation

Aid workers are defined as “the employees and associated personnel (paid and volunteers) of not-for-profit aid agencies (both national and international) that provide material and technical assistance in humanitarian relief contexts.”¹

The database’s unit of analysis is an *incident*, which may include one or several of the following acts of coercion or violence against aid workers (the list below is taken directly from the Codebook):

- Killing;
- Kidnapping or abduction by non-state or criminal actors for more than 24 hours;
- Serious wounding, defined as injuries that [...] require medical attention;
- Detention or arrest by host state authorities, police, or de facto authorities for more than 24 hours;
- Rape or sexual assault.²

The data is sourced and verified by human coders on a daily basis, drawing primarily from online news and social media. The organization also partners with a select number of aid agencies and operational security entities that may directly provide information about incidents involving their staff, as well as assist with cross-checking and verification.

All incidents are geocoded with the highest possible precision based on open-source information or, in rare cases, confidential data provided by partners. When a precise geolocation cannot be established, the database records at least the relevant municipality or a nearby publicly listed place or landmark.

¹ Humanitarian Outcomes, “Aid Worker Security Database (AWSDB) Codebook,” 2025, <https://humanitarianoutcomes.org/sites/default/files/2025-09/Aid%20Worker%20Security%20Database%20Public%20Codebook%20May%202025.pdf>, p.3.

² Ibid.

The incidents are coded across five categories of variables:

- Spatial data information (location);
- Victim descriptive data (information on affected aid workers, including their gender, type of employment, and organizational affiliation);
- Incident descriptive data (number killed, injured, or kidnapped; type and context of the attack; etc.);
- Perpetrator information (any available details on alleged perpetrators at both the individual and group levels, as well as the motive, if known);
- Source information.

Detailed information on the content of each variable, as well as other features of the dataset, can be found in the publicly available and regularly updated Codebook (also translated to French, Spanish, and Arabic) on the project's official website.³

Scope conditions

The dataset does not include incidents involving “UN peacekeeping personnel, human rights workers, election monitors, or purely political, religious, or advocacy organizations.” It also excludes incidents such as “road accidents, illness, [mine clearance accidents], or incidents that occur to family members of humanitarian staff.”⁴ Additionally, the dataset does not include the names of individual victims or survivors in order to protect their confidentiality and ensure the safety of them and their families.⁵

Usage

As of November 2025, it includes 5,150 incidents coded across 44 variables and 97 countries, including:

- Ukraine (66 incidents; 2014–2025; 164 persons affected);
- Chechnya (26 incidents; 1997–2009; 44 persons affected);
- Tajikistan (4 incidents; 1997–2001; 24 persons affected);
- Kyrgyzstan (3 incidents; 2010, 2013, 2020; 3 persons affected);
- Poland (2 incidents; 2022, 2024; 2 persons affected);
- Armenia (1 incident; 2013; 1 person affected);
- Azerbaijan (1 incident; 2018; 5 persons affected);
- Georgia (1 incident; 2000; 3 persons affected).

³ Humanitarian Outcomes, “About the Data: Aid Worker Security Database,” [www.aidworkersecurity.org](https://www.aidworkersecurity.org/about), n.d., <https://www.aidworkersecurity.org/about>.

⁴ Humanitarian Outcomes, “Aid Worker Security Database (AWSDB) Codebook,” 2025, <https://humanitarianoutcomes.org/sites/default/files/2025-09/Aid%20Worker%20Security%20Database%20Public%20Codebook%20May%202025.pdf>, p. 4.

⁵ Ibid, p. 6.

The variables include:

- Incident ID;
- Year;
- Month;
- Day;
- Country code;
- Country;
- Region (within a country);
- District (within a region of a country);
- City;
- A set of binary variables for the type of organization (UN, INGO, ICRC, NRCS or IFRC, NNGO, and Other);
- A set of variables for the number of national personnel killed, wounded, kidnapped, or detained in an incident;
- A set of variables for the number of international personnel killed, wounded, kidnapped, or detained in an incident;
- A set of binary variables for gender (male, female, or unknown);
- Means of attack;
- Attack context;
- Location (including separate variables for latitude and longitude);
- Motive;
- Actor type;
- Actor name;
- Details (textual description of the coded data);
- Verification (“Verified,” “Pending,” or “Archived” — for cases where additional information may be provided upon request);
- Source (“Focal point,” “Media,” “Official report,” “ACLED”).⁶

Upon request, the organization may also provide data on deconfliction markers, which is currently not available publicly.

The database is entirely downloadable as a .csv file, and should be cited as follows: *“Humanitarian Outcomes, Aid Worker Security Database, aidworkersecurity.org.”*

In addition to the database, the organization provides regularly updated summary statistics and graphs for each variable,⁷ as well as in-depth reports.⁸

⁶ ACLED is “an independent, impartial conflict monitor providing real-time data and analysis on violent conflict and protest in all countries and territories across the world.” See <https://acleddata.com/>.

⁷ Humanitarian Outcomes, “Reports and Briefing Papers: Aid Worker Security Database,”

Humanitarian Outcomes, August 19, 2025, <https://www.aidworkersecurity.org/reports>.

⁸ Ibid.

As of November 2025, according to Google Scholar, the database was cited in over 500 academic papers; examples include:

- Nanami Morokuma and Cindy H. Chiu, “Trends and Characteristics of Security Incidents Involving Aid Workers in Health Care Settings: A 20-Year Review,” *Prehospital and Disaster Medicine* 34, no. 03 (June 2019): 265–73, <https://doi.org/10.1017/s1049023x19004333>.
- Kristian Hoelscher, Jason Miklian, and Håvard Mogleiv Nygård, “Conflict, Peacekeeping, and Humanitarian Security: Understanding Violent Attacks against Aid Workers,” *International Peacekeeping* 24, no. 4 (May 17, 2017): 538–65, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13533312.2017.1321958>.
- Neil Narang and Jessica A. Stanton, “A Strategic Logic of Attacking Aid Workers: Evidence from Violence in Afghanistan,” *International Studies Quarterly* 61, no. 1 (March 1, 2017): 38–51, <https://doi.org/10.1093/isq/sqw053>.
- Valeska P. Korff et al., “The Impact of Humanitarian Context Conditions and Individual Characteristics on Aid Worker Retention,” *Disasters* 39, no. 3 (January 9, 2015): 522–45, <https://doi.org/10.1111/disa.12119>.
- Robert I.S. Macpherson and Frederick M. Burkle, “Humanitarian Aid Workers: The Forgotten First Responders,” *Prehospital and Disaster Medicine* 36, no. 1 (November 3, 2020): 1–4, <https://doi.org/10.1017/s1049023x20001326>.

Funding

The project is funded by the Governments of Australia and Canada. Previously, it was also supported by the governments of the United States and Ireland.

Note

This data review was produced by Anhelina Hrytsei, a Master’s student in Peace and Conflict Studies at Uppsala University, as part of an Erasmus Traineeship at the Research Center for East European Studies at the University of Bremen.